

D2.2: Updated Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

BoF	Birds of a Feather
DANS	Data Archiving and Networked Services
EC	European Commission
EGU	European Geosciences Union
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
ISC	International Science Council
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDA	Research Data Alliance
ReSA	Research Software Alliance
RSE	Research Software Engineering
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation
WG	Working Group

Executive Summary

This deliverable outlines the high-level plan for the RDA TIGER project to maximise the a) service awareness and dissemination of project outputs, and b) the communication service offered to RDA Working Groups (WGs). It presents the strategic phases, objectives and priorities, outlines planned communication activities, and carries out an analysis of the expected service users, also considering the service’s target audiences and stakeholders. The document also provides a brief overview of the communications materials that have already been developed as part of the communication kit, and outlines the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that WP2 will follow. Finally, this document presents the anticipated risks, and touches on potential plans for the exploitation of the project results.

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1. Introduction

The RDA TIGER project aims to provide services to facilitate and support RDA Working Groups in order to produce quality outputs, resulting in concrete alignment, harmonisation, and standardisation of Open Science developments and technologies globally. In particular, the project will directly contribute to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership, by supporting (via the RDA Working Groups) the international engagement and alignment of policies, technologies, methodologies, practices and other outputs of EOSC-related and other European Open Science developments. It will develop and offer a service platform for these Working Groups, effectively identifying key partners for the groups, and increasing their work efficiency by facilitation, ensuring international connectivity, and other support actions to produce optimum results, and ultimately maximising the impact WG results have on the EOSC, global Open Science, and society.

RDA TIGER leverages the demonstrably effective instrument of community-driven RDA Working Groups and the foundations of EOSC, RDA, CODATA, Research Software Alliance (ReSA), and the Open Science movement in general, and provides a way to efficiently use the RDA platform for internationalisation and standardisation of research outputs that allow science to be reproducible and scrutinised. The RDA TIGER service platform includes planning, engagement, landscaping communication, facilitation and finalisation services to the Working Groups, maximising the WG outputs, and their impact.

The communication tasks in WP2 planned within this document follow three lines of activity: 1) service awareness, promotion of the RDA TIGER service platform, and dissemination of project outputs, 2) the communications service offered to RDA WGs, and to a lesser extent 3) internal project communications. At the strategy and planning level, the document examines communications mostly in relation to point 1, as detailed. Bespoke planning for WG communication strategies as part of point 2 will take place with the input of each WG Co-Chair and throughout the project lifetime. D2.1 in month 6 will include an Annex with the bespoke strategies for each WG. The document also describes the customer profiles for the RDA TIGER services, outlines the available resources that will be leveraged, sets out targets and key performance indicators, and produces an analysis of the relevant stakeholders.

2. Target Audience

2.1. RDA Community

The RDA TIGER main target audience is the RDA Community. Any individual or organisation, regardless of profession or discipline, with an interest in reducing the barriers to the sharing and re-use of data and who agrees to RDA's guiding principles¹ can join RDA. The RDA membership consists of professionals across fields: Academia and Research, Government and Public Services, Small and

¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/about-rda>

Medium Enterprises, with Policy and Funding agencies, IT Consultants/Developers, Large Enterprises and Press/Media. The membership also spans across 150 countries and all continents (Europe comprising the majority with over 50%). At the time of writing, the RDA has 13512 members, 48 WGs, 63 IGs, and one Community of Practice (CoP).

Figure 1. RDA Membership Geographical Distribution as of February 2023

Within the RDA Community, the RDA TIGER project’s target audience are the RDA WGs, both existing ones and new ones (that will be created during the lifetime of the project, with its support). RDA WGs run usually over a short term period of 18 months, and concentrate on developing a single well-defined output. RDA WGs have been proven to be extremely efficient in providing internationally accepted solutions for many research data-oriented issues, leading to widely recognized practices² - examples of which are the CoreTrustSeal³ and FAIRSharing Registry⁴.

² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/catalogue>

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-coretrustseal-adoption-story-across-domains-and-regions>

⁴ <https://rd-alliance.org/group/fairsharing-registry-connecting-data-policies-standards-databases-wg/outcomes/fairsharing>

Figure 2. RDA Groups Overview: Working and Interest Groups

2.2. EOSC and the wider Open Science Landscape

This section touches on a number of indicative target audiences of the RDA TIGER WG outputs as identified at the Grant Agreement stage.

- EOSC related initiatives (e.g. Horizon2020 and Horizon Europe projects, EOSC-A task forces);
- EOSC users and service providers (e.g. research infrastructures);
- European Member states policy makers and funders;
- Open Science national experts;
- the beneficiaries of more transparent, FAIR and effective scientific practices: scientists and the society as a whole (who will benefit from the outputs of the RDA groups).
- The wider International data community

Further and more specifically: RDA Group and/or Output target audiences will likely be identified during the project lifetime as more WGs use the RDA TIGER service. The updated list will be provided in D2.3: Report on the progress of European national network engagement in RDA TIGER WGs and D2.4: Overview of the communication service provision and lessons learned in months 30 and 36 respectively.

Finally, WP2 will work closely with WP3 Landscape & Engagement to incorporate results and communications contacts from the following areas: research evaluation, monitoring, reproducibility, multidisciplinary cooperation and large data sharing mechanisms.

3. RDA TIGER Communication Service

RDA TIGER will provide a comprehensive communications approach associated with each WG. This is vital to ensure that the RDA community is aware of WG developments, to facilitate full buy-in from potential WG members, to avoid duplication of work and to be made aware of updates at each stage of the WG.

This section describes the action plan in response to tasks 2.1 (service creation) and 2.2 (communications and dissemination service provision and Awareness).

3.1. Communications Service Description

Throughout the duration of the RDA TIGER project, one of the primary aims of WP2 is to create and maintain a public profile for the services (Task 2.1) in order to:

- Attract potential users (new or existing WGs);
- Promote the services provided and their benefits, and;
- Provide updates on the progress of the project

Beyond service awareness, WP2 is tasked with supporting RDA WGs with all their communications and outreach requirements (Task 2.2). Figure 3 below shows the role and positioning of the communications service (Service 'C') within the RDA TIGER service platform.

Figure 3. RDA TIGER services

3.1.1. Communication activities per WG stage

This section provides an overview of the specific activities that will be undertaken by WP2 in support of the RDA WGs⁵, in coordination with the Facilitation service and in response to Group applications for facilitation and communications support.

The calls for WG group support and funded support will be open on a rolling basis, with applications being submitted all year around. There will be four cut-off dates (May, August, November and February) during each year of the RDA TIGER project. Each WG supported by RDA TIGER will receive tailored communication support based on consultations with the Group Chairs following a successful application. The full RDA TIGER grant management process and timelines is described in *D6.6 Rules of Operation for the Selection Committee*.

The table below summarises each step of the communications service.

⁵ The complete service definition is available on the shared Google Drive:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1IQiBgymQP_qdMISXbvEJ7qLkKA9hAt8fuRugOSDBfE/edit#.

Table 1. RDA Communication Service stages

C1: Idea Dissemination (Working Group Start)	
C1.1	Service request submission management
C1.2	Coordination with the Facilitator (internal)
C1.3	Coordination with the application submitters (external)
C1.4	Creation of WG communication plan
C1.5	Outreach to potential WG members
C2: Internal and external WG Communications (WG work period)	
C2.1	Coordination with the Facilitator
C2.2	Coordination with the WG
C2.3	Creation OR Update of the WG Communication Plan
C2.4	Internal Communication Services
C2.5	External Communication services
Dissemination of outputs (WG end period)	
C3.1	Coordination with the Facilitator
C3.2	Coordination with the WG
C3.3	Creation OR Update of the WG Communication Plan
C3.4	Outputs and Adoption Promotion Services

3.1.1.1. WG starting

Figure 4. C1 (Idea dissemination) service blueprint

This service provides the initial dissemination on the WG idea/topic and support in finding potential WG members. Communication tools used in this format include the RDA and other multiplier networks (e.g., EOSC Association, GÉANT, OpenAIRE, EGI, EUDAT), social media, and website announcements. Special activities, such as direct contact, participation in conferences/workshops, or even special planning workshops can be organised if necessary. The objective of this service is increased awareness of the initial WG idea and attraction of interested WG members.

C1.2: Coordination with the Facilitator (internal)

Once an application for TIGER support has been accepted, the Facilitator and the Communications Lead liaise in order to begin the planning process for the WG and the outreach activities supporting it (dissemination email, key points for individual dissemination plan, definition of specific aspects (if any) that the Facilitator requires from the Communications Lead).

C1.3: Coordination with the application submitters (external)

Alongside the Facilitator, WP2 will meet with the application submitters and discuss the specific outreach channels and materials required in order to target potential WG members. Specific tools that will be used include:

- Mailing lists;
- direct communication with individuals;
- RDA website news items and newsletters;
- social media;
- approaching partner institutions and other external contacts;
- presentation in 3rd party events (workshops, other Group meetings, bespoke events presenting the Group idea and gathering interest, etc);
- other (bespoke materials requested by the submitters, subject to resource availability).

C1.4: Creation of WG communication plan

Following input from the Senior Facilitator and the WG, the Communications Lead will put a communications plan in place, on which all activities will be based.

C1.5: Outreach to potential WG members

The above actions are in coordination with the assigned Facilitator (Service F1 in figure 3), and are informed by the Landscape activity.

3.1.1.2. WG working period

C.2: Internal and external WG Communications (WG work period).

This service provides internal WG communication support, such as WG website upkeep, internal contact information management, periodic internal bulletins (email lists), communication tools management and provision (Slack, etc). It also provides external dissemination and communication services, such as periodic progress updates in website and email lists, management of external communication lists related to WG, dissemination preparation in RDA Plenaries and International Data Weeks, effective dissemination of progress to interested bodies identified in A1 and A2 services (as presented in figure 3).

C2.1: Coordination with the Facilitator

Once an application has been accepted OR the group has progressed from Initiation (C1) to WG work period (C2), the Facilitator and the Communications lead liaise to either begin the planning process for the Group (if new user) or review and update the individual communication plan, and coordinate activities. The Facilitator and Communications team will review/plan the outreach activities supporting the group (dissemination email, key points for individual dissemination plan and define specific aspects (if any) that the Facilitator requires from the Communications lead.

Given the overlap in activities, this is an important step to avoid duplication and ensure efficiency.

Figure 5. C2 (WG working period) service blueprint

C2.2: Coordination with the WG

Alongside the Facilitator, WP2 will meet with the WG and discuss the specific set of services and any outreach materials required; the following list is an example of internal and external facing activities that will be undertaken:

Internal Communication Services

- Group webpage updates and maintenance
- Group mailing list management
- Communication tools management and provision (e.g., Slack, Google Drive, etc.)
- Group meetings support (in coordination with the Facilitator)
- Communication with RDA Secretariat as and when needed

External Communication services

- Group progress and general news dissemination
 - internal within RDA with website posts, banners and sliders, news items and RDA Global newsletter items
 - external to RDA leveraging partner networks
- External mailing list management (if applicable)
- Plenary preparation support
- Graphic materials creation

- Event management support (in coordination with the Facilitator)

C2.3: Creation OR Update of the WG Communication Plan

Following input from the Facilitator and the Group, the Communications Lead will put a communications plan in place, on which all activities will be based. A clear start and end period of all activities is defined.

C2.4: Internal Communication Services

The following internal communications services can be provided to the WGs. These services will be discussed and defined during C2.1 processes.

- Group page updates and maintenance
- Group mailing list management
- Communication tools management and provision (e.g., Slack)
- Group meetings support (in coordination with the Facilitator)

C2.5: External Communication services

The Group will also be able to benefit from the following external-facing activities:

- Progress and news dissemination
- External mailing list management (if applicable)
- Plenary preparation support
- Graphic materials creation
- Event management support (in coordination with the Facilitator)

3.1.1.3. WG ending

C3.2: Coordination with the WG

Alongside the facilitator, WP2 will meet with the WG and discuss the specific set of services and any outreach materials required during this stage.

C3.3: Creation OR Update of the WG Communication Plan

Following input from the Facilitator and the Group, the Communications Lead will put a communications plan in place, on which all activities will be based. A clear start and end period of all activities is defined.

C3.4: Outputs and Adoption Promotion Services

During this stage, WP2 will undertake WG-Output specific targeted dissemination of the WG outputs, including social media, websites, targeted events, and other direct mechanisms (dissemination materials, podcasts) to ensure the awareness of the WG output in the relevant target groups. These target communities are defined in the service O1, and can be further developed based on the progress from services O2 and O3 for this WG output.

Figure 6. C3 (WG ending) service blueprint

The Group will have selected from the following services:

- Dissemination of Outputs within RDA (website posts, news items, member outreach, inclusion in RDA events),
- Dissemination of Outputs externally to RDA (utilising co-chair and RDA TIGER partner networks as well as those identified by the Group during the initial onboarding stages)
- Dissemination of Outputs to specific Adopter communities (in coordination with O services)
- Creation of graphics to accompany output
- Organisation of bespoke events and webinars to promote the output

3.2. User profiles

As RDA TIGER is a project designing and delivering services, the communication strategy is driven by the service users and their needs. The document takes the perspective that the users are the entire Working Group membership rather than the Group Co-chairs, as the project and service objectives and to improve Group efficiency and Output quality. That said, the service mainly interacts with the Group Co-chairs who lead on behalf of the Groups and influence all processes, and as a result, user profiles are based on their characteristics.

Examining the different user types for RDA services will enable the project to tailor the communication activities and strategy (which is of particular importance as communications is also a service provided to the Groups), and also potentially further inform service provision as the project progresses from its piloting stage.

This section will present three profiles: 1) New RDA WGs (Co-chairs are experienced RDA members), 2) New RDA WGs (Co-chairs are new or non-RDA members) and 3) Existing RDA WGs (Co-chairs are experienced RDA members).

3.2.1. New RDA WGs (Co-chairs as experienced RDA members)

User description

This user profile refers to RDA Birds of a Feather (BoF) group⁶ organisers, and subsequently RDA WGs, who have applied for RDA TIGER support and their application has been accepted. This user is an experienced RDA member, they may already be members or Co-chairs of other RDA Groups, and have a good grasp of RDA processes, the community and the WG creation lifecycle and procedure. This is important as it informs the level of service (communication and otherwise) that will be delivered to this Working Group.

Services used

The user may interact with the whole portfolio of RDA TIGER services: Landscape and Engagement, Facilitation, Communications. From a communications perspective and following figure 3, this profile will use: a) Initial idea dissemination support (C1), b) Internal and External WG Communications (C2) and Dissemination of outputs (C3).

Pain points

From a Communication service perspective, this user, given their experience with the RDA Community and processes, 1) may already have a complete idea of who should be WG members and Co-chairs, but lacks capacity and dedicated effort for the time-consuming outreach tasks, 2) may lack tools and capacity to perform outreach activities to promote their work externally and to coordinate internal communications within the Group, and 3) might not have the appropriate connections outside of RDA for wider dissemination of WG results or the appropriate tools for this task.

Solutions offered

The Communication Service will provide in-kind staff to support 1) initial idea dissemination and outreach to the individuals that may want to be WG members or co-chairs, 2) internal and external WG communications, while 3) also working with the BoF organiser to identify potential networks outside of RDA, also handling all related outreach to these new external facing connections.

⁶ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/creating-and-managing-rda-groups/creating-or-joining-birds-feather-group

3.2.2. New RDA WGs (Co-chairs as RDA newcomers)

User description

This user profile refers to Birds of a Feather (BoF) organisers, and subsequently RDA WGs, who have applied for RDA TIGER support and their application has been accepted. This user is not an experienced RDA co-chair, or they may even be an RDA newcomer. They do not have awareness of RDA processes, the community and the WG creation lifecycle and procedure. This fact informs the level of service (communication and otherwise) that will be delivered to this Working Group.

Services used

The user may interact with the whole portfolio of RDA TIGER services: Landscape and Engagement, Facilitation, Communications. From a communications perspective and following figure 3 this profile will use: a) Initial idea dissemination support (C1), b) Internal and External WG Communications (C2) and Dissemination of outputs (C3).

Pain points

From a Communication service perspective, this user, given their lack of experience with the RDA Community and processes, 1) is at a disadvantage with regards to finding other Co-chairs or RDA Group members, 2) may lack capacity to perform outreach activities to promote their work externally and to coordinate internal communications, and 3) might not have the appropriate connections inside or outside of RDA for wider dissemination of WG results.

Solutions offered

The Communication Service will increase in-kind effort to support 1) the identification of communication tools and channels; the Group will need increased facilitation effort from WP5, but also from WP2 as the RDA TIGER Facilitator and Communications Coordinator align to support the new Group in finding appropriate WG members, Co-chairs, and both WP2 and WP5 working with the BoF organisers to identify potential routes of dissemination both at WG start, work period and finalisation stages, 2) internal and external WG communications, while 3) also working with the BoF organiser to identify potential networks outside of RDA and within the RDA membership, also handling all related outreach to these connections.

3.2.3. Existing RDA WGs

User description

This user profile refers to WGs that are in their working or finalisation period, who have applied for RDA TIGER support and their application has been accepted. This will be a relatively experienced RDA co-chair given that the Group has likely formally been meeting for a period of time. They have awareness of RDA processes, the community and the WG creation lifecycle and procedure. This fact informs the level of service (communication and otherwise) that will be delivered to this Working Group.

Services used

The user may interact with the whole portfolio of RDA TIGER services: Landscape and Engagement, Facilitation, Communications. From a communications perspective and following Figure 3, this profile will use: a) Internal and External WG Communications (C2) and b) Dissemination of Outputs (C3).

Pain points

From a Communication Service perspective, this user given their experience with the RDA Community and processes, 1) may lack capacity and dedicated effort to carry out outreach tasks, 2) may lack tools to perform outreach activities to promote their work externally and to coordinate internal communications within the Group, and 3) might not have the appropriate connections outside of RDA for wider dissemination of WG results or the appropriate tools for this task.

Solutions offered

The Communication service will provide 1) in-kind staff to support communications endeavours, 2) will provide tools to facilitate more effective outreach and 3) will work with the Group to identify potential networks outside of RDA, also handling all related outreach to these new external facing connections.

4. Stakeholders

The following high-level stakeholders have been identified both for the project as a whole (service platform) and for the communication service offered to WGs in particular. Table 1 below lists these stakeholders alongside their relationship to the project and the communication channels that will be used to reach them.

Table 2. RDA TIGER stakeholders

Stakeholder	Connection to RDA TIGER	Communication Channels
RDA Membership	Target audience of RDA TIGER, benefits from high quality WG Outputs and efficient meetings. Potential adopters of Group Outputs exist in this stakeholder group.	RDA Global and EU channels (web platform, Plenaries, social media, other RDA events). Targeted engagement of membership sub-groups depending on supported WG bespoke strategies and needs as defined in discussions with co-chairs.
RDA Group co-chairs	Main target audience of RDA TIGER services, benefits from in-kind support and direct grants.	RDA Global channels (web platform, Plenaries, social media, other RDA events).
RDA Governance	The Governance structure has direct interest into the testing	Direct engagement.

Stakeholder	Connection to RDA TIGER	Communication Channels
	(and success) of the RDA TIGER model due to the potential for it developing into a paid service for the RDA. Better supported WGs also result in more professionalised RDA processes and Outputs, which aligns with the current RDA Strategic plan ⁷ .	
Funder’s Forum	The Funders’ Forum provides potential WG Output adopters from funding organisations.	Virtual meetings, Plenaries, direct engagement if a Funder is identified as stakeholder for a supported WG.
Industry	The new RDA framework for Industry collaborations ⁸ creates a pathway for engaging the public sector; apart from this being of interest for WGs as being a pool of potential adopters, the recent collaboration with Oracle creates a link for privately facilitated/funded Groups within RDA, which is of interest to RDA TIGER from a sustainability and exploitation perspective.	Plenaries, exhibition booths at third party events, targeted engagement, social media.
EOSC Community	The EOSC community provides potential WG Output adopters at a higher level; more specifically, EOSC is a critical stakeholder given the strict requirement for supported WGs to align with its priorities and objectives.	EOSC Focus, EOSC Forum, HE WG, events (e.g., EOSC Symposium, direct engagement)
ESFRI / Cluster projects	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	RDA Global and EU channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other events,

⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/about-rda/rda-strategic-plan-2020-2023>

⁸ <https://rd-alliance.org/rda-engaging-industry-%E2%80%93-new-framework-collaboration>

Stakeholder	Connection to RDA TIGER	Communication Channels
Individual Researchers & Research Communities	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	RDA Global and EU channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other events, WG contacts, direct engagement.
(e-)Research Infrastructures	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	RDA Global and EU channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other events, WG contacts, direct engagement.
Research funders	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	RDA Global and EU channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other events, WG contacts, exhibition booths, direct engagement.
Data Stewards and Research support staff	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	RDA Global and EU channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other events, WG contacts, direct engagement.
Policymakers	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	RDA Global and EU channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other events, WG contacts, exhibition booths, direct engagement.
Research institutions	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	RDA Global and EU channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other events, WG contacts, direct engagement.
Open Science / Research Clouds / Commons	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	RDA Global and EU channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other events, WG contacts, direct engagement.
Repositories/archives	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	RDA Global and EU channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other events, WG contacts, direct engagement.

Stakeholder	Connection to RDA TIGER	Communication Channels
Research software Engineers / software developers	Potential WG Recommendation and Output adopters, and additional expertise from which RDA can draw.	RDA Global and EU channels, web platform, Plenaries, social media, other events, WG contacts, direct engagement.

4.1. Communication Strategic priorities

While the RDA Community as described in [section 2.1](#) remains the main and primary target audience as well as the stakeholder who mostly benefits from RDA TIGER services, certain stakeholders have been identified that stand out for their strategic importance to the organisation, as well as the immediately accessible wealth of expertise that they can offer, such as the RDA National Networks (elsewhere in project documentation referred to as ‘National Nodes’) and a number of European initiatives. In addition, a need has been identified to expand the outreach efforts beyond the existing RDA community; this will benefit the RDA at a Global level, and also provide additional pools of expertise to the supported WGs.

4.1.1. Engaging the RDA national networks (nodes)

The RDA national networks (nodes)⁹ will be engaged during the project in order to gain additional experts, local viewpoints and challenge, and channel these resources into the RDA WGs. The nodes may also be used to find Output adopters through their links to multiple European organisations. Increased engagement of the regions is a strategic priority for both the RDA Global and the European office, so outreach to the nodes will be prioritised and their expertise will be leveraged.

WP2 will engage the national nodes through direct outreach but also through a number of workshops and participation in regional meetings. Bespoke plans may be put in place if a need is identified in consultation with supported WGs.

4.1.2. Beyond the RDA Community

EOSC Community

European Open Science cloud related organisations, projects, and users of EOSC. Initiatives, projects, organisations and experts outside of Europe related to Open Science, FAIR development, or similar activities to EOSC. Experts and initiatives in the European countries on same areas. Research Data Alliance members (for use/creation of the services). Policy makers, research assessment developers and research funding organisations.

Project Partners as amplifiers

⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-europe-national-nodes>

Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)¹⁰, an Institute of the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW), supports researchers making their data FAIR and available for reuse, by offering technical data-facilities, training, and expertise. DANS provides training at the European and national level and performs research into sustained access to digital information. Sharing and gaining expertise through participation in European and national projects is an important part of their activities. As coordinator of FAIRsFAIR and the subsequent FAIR-IMPACT project, DANS helped shape EOSC in this area. The main activities in the RDA TIGER are based on their connectivity globally and in Europe, with resulting help on engaging key communities, and most importantly, due to their strong experience and knowledge on research output development, policy interactions and technical development, providing guidance for the RDA TIGER WGs on output creation. They are also the facility providing the RDA Maintenance Platform.

CODATA¹¹ is the Committee on Data of the International Science Council (ISC, previously ICSU, the International Council of Scientific Unions). It was founded in 1966 following the realisation of the need for global coordination of scientific data collections, standardisation and quality that followed the International Geophysical Year of 1958-9. Among CODATA's major contributions to the science of data include the recommended values for the fundamental physical constants which now underpin the entire SI System. CODATA has also been prominent in the development of data policies, standards and key components of the data infrastructure. More recently, the Executive Director, Simon Hodson, chaired the EC's Expert Group that produced the Turning FAIR into Reality Report, and was co-chair of the Expert Advisory Committee for the recently adopted UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science. CODATA brings strong connections with international scientific representative bodies, including UNESCO, ISC and international scientific unions for a range of research areas.

The **Netherlands eScience Center**¹² is the Dutch national centre of expertise for innovative software solutions in academic research. Bringing together knowledge, people and institutions, the eScience Center builds and applies software to enhance the use of digital technology in research. The eScience Center also examines the ways in which open science principles can responsibly be applied to software; this includes the FAIR principles and other initiatives in this area. The eScience Center stimulates the development and publication of research software that supports the reproducibility of research results. The eScience Center closely collaborates with international eScience, software sustainability and research software initiatives, including research software engineering (RSE) communities and the Research Software Alliance (ReSA). As the connection to ReSA, ESC can provide the gateway to Research Software related initiatives and organisations.

ESFRI Cluster projects

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) was established to shape collaboration in five thematic areas to pave the way for Open Access data for the EOSC. Through its cluster projects [...] ESFRI steers the integration and consolidation of thematic e-infrastructure

¹⁰ <https://dans.knaw.nl/en>

¹¹ <https://codata.org/>

¹² <https://www.esciencecenter.nl>

platforms in preparation for connecting them to EOSC. The ESFRI cluster projects implement interfaces to integrate computer and data management solutions to create cross-border, interdisciplinary and open cooperation spaces for European researchers¹³.

RDA TIGER will utilise the ESFRIs to gain access to wider audiences for WG results; in particular, these connections will be used for the dissemination of draft Recommendations during the Community feedback stage.

5. Communication and Outreach Strategy

5.1. Objectives

The objectives of the RDA TIGER communication strategy and by extension the communication service and activities can be summarised as follows:

- a. Maximise service uptake through the provision of service awareness to the RDA Community and potential Users;
- b. Maximise the impact RDA WG outputs have on the EOSC, global Open Science, and society by helping WGs reach the appropriate stakeholders and communities, whether they are in idea dissemination/Group outreach stage, or output dissemination stage;
- c. Facilitate smoother and more efficient operations within RDA WGs through the provision of tailored communications services and plans;
- d. Directly contribute to the European Open Science Cloud Partnership, by supporting (via the Working Groups) the international engagement and alignment of policies, technologies, methodologies, practices and other outputs of EOSC-related and other European Open Science developments; and
- e. Facilitate communication internally within the RDA TIGER project partners.

5.2. Strategic Phases

The communication strategy can be divided into three stages, based on the maturity of the RDA TIGER services and therefore the variability of needs throughout the lifetime of the project. This section will provide a brief overview of each Strategic Phases, outlining the unique needs and goals. It should be noted that this chapter focuses on communications as an integral process of the overall project and RDA TIGER service provision, and not of the communication service as offered to the WGs. The specific activities carried out for the RDA WGs follow the objectives outlined above, and are detailed in section [Communication activities per WG stage](#).

5.2.1. Phase 1: Service Awareness (Pilot Stage)

Focus

¹³ <https://eosc-portal.eu/esfri-thematic-cluster-projects>

The first year of the RDA TIGER project will focus on creating service awareness within the RDA Community. It is a priority in this first strategic phase, as it is necessary in order to facilitate service uptake and allow the services to mature and progress into the next phase. That said, maintaining service awareness throughout the lifetime of the project and enriching the tools with which it is delivered as the project and services gather experience is equally crucial in order to ensure continuous uptake, and to allow for any subsequent sustainability considerations for the RDA TIGER funding model to transition to a standard part of the RDA Europe (and indeed potentially RDA Global) Business.

As such, service awareness can be considered the main communication and dissemination activity of the project, given that it is continuous through all phases.

An additional objective of this stage is quantifying the effort for each of the Communication services and in order to be able to consolidate the full service offering in subsequent stages. This endeavour applies to the whole Service Platform.

Tools and means of dissemination

In this strategic phase, the communication service and strategy will focus on creating and publicising the RDA TIGER brand and planning the means for effective dissemination of RDA TIGER activities and services to the RDA Community, as well as designing and implementing the corresponding communication plans in order to meet this objective. In summary, the objective will be achieved through the creation and maintenance of the online presence and brand of the project, the dissemination of the services and RDA WG opportunities in general using the RDA web platform, social media, conference booths, RDA plenary presentations/posters, specialised workshops (targets identified in the Landscape monitoring below), and other bespoke traditional dissemination tools.

The service will also leverage the communication channels available to the project partners. One of the goals in this strategic phase is to target audiences globally, so extending the activities to RDA, CODATA, ReSA and other meetings also outside of Europe is important.

Target audiences

The target audiences in this phase are: WG participants and co-chairs, EOSC projects/initiatives, Open Science experts/organisations, research evaluation organisations.

5.2.2. Phase 2: Service Growth and Maturity

Focus

This strategic phase is expected to kick off in the second year of the project (January - December 2025), after the end of the Pilot stage and through to the end of the project. During this stage, it is presumed that the RDA Community is aware of the RDA TIGER project, and Phase 1 has met its objectives. The project is now in its growth stage, having taken on additional Groups, defined and improved its services, and been able to report tangible results.

From a service perspective, in this phase the efforts will focus on promoting success stories, use cases and Group outputs, in order to cultivate the public image of a fully developed professional service. The objective is to shift the message from 'service kick-off' to 'successful service delivery' while

maintaining service awareness and working to increase uptake; these activities are informed, updated and improved as the team gathers lessons learned, experience and shareable success stories through a richer portfolio of users. By extension, a mature and successful service will be well placed to maximise the impact RDA WG outputs and support the work of RDA; this remains the underlying objective in this phase.

Following the Pilot stage of the project, the service quality indicators will be re-evaluated and depending on outcomes corrective actions will be implemented.

Tools and means of dissemination

In addition to the tools outlined in 4.2.1, this phase will utilise events and webinars, digital materials/outputs, testimonials, interviews with service users and other means as needed. Depending on the portfolio of supported RDA WGs, the appropriate tools and paths of dissemination will be selected in order to reach the relevant audiences.

Target audience

The audience remains the same: WG participants and co-chairs, EOSC projects/initiatives, Open Science experts/organisations, research evaluation organisations.

5.2.2.1. Service maturity and next steps

During phase two, it can be expected that the RDA TIGER service will reach relative maturity, after providing its services for three years. While not within the scope of this project, the final six months of the project can potentially be used to analyse use cases for the RDA TIGER service model as a paid service provided to Groups by the RDA, as well as as best practice for Facilitating Expert Groups. The success of communications strategy as described in Phases 1 and 2 will influence the outcome of these analyses.

5.3. Impact

On the service platform dissemination level, the RDA TIGER Communication strategy can directly impact service uptake within RDA Community (but also outwith with new WGs forming), depending on the success of the promotion campaigns in particular during the first year of the project. Being one of the services offered to RDA Groups, the communications activities and specifically ensuring Outputs have a dedicated communication strategy and reach the appropriate audiences through the appropriate and most efficient channels, will help increase the impact of the Groups work and the Outputs themselves.

As a service offered to the RDA Groups, successful and effective implementation of the communication activities also directly contribute to the following high level project objectives surrounding international alignment:

- creation, sharing, management and re-use of research outputs (e.g. data, software, publications, workflows, protocols, and methodologies);
- facilitating scientific multidisciplinary cooperation;
- increasing FAIRness, openness and quality of scientific research in Europe and globally;
- creating new communities [and] connections [...] for future actions in Europe, and possible concurrent support actions in other areas.¹⁴

6. Communication Plan

The RDA TIGER communication strategy will be implemented through the Communication Plan outlined in this section. The Plan will facilitate the dissemination of project results to the relevant communities and stakeholders ensuring service awareness and leveraging existing communication channels through project partners. It will also amplify the supported WG impact; finally, the plan will facilitate internal communications coordination. The Communication Plan is coordinated by WP2.

6.1. Service Platform promotion campaign tracker

WP2 will plan its activities around creating and maintaining service awareness and promoting overall service platform activities using a communication tracker¹⁵. The tracker will record all dissemination networks available to the project as they are identified through interaction with the Groups. It will also plan activities on a monthly basis and coordinate distribution across all available channels (social media, websites, newsletters, etc). This tracker will also record progress on the bespoke communication plans created as part of the communications service.

6.2. Bespoke Group communication plans

The Communications Lead in coordination with the Facilitator and the Group co-chairs will create a communication plan for each of the supported Groups that request to avail of the communication service. The communication plans will follow a standard format¹⁶ and take in to consideration the following components:

- Objective
- Target audiences
- Dissemination channels and tools
- Day-to-day communication schedule

As part of the RDA TIGER Pilot stage and based on both initial discussions at GA stage and recent follow-up assessments, the following pre-selected Groups will be supported as a minimum, with the potential for pilot cases to increase:

¹⁴ RDA TIGER grant agreement

¹⁵ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1OKQcd3OrZWaqrI9OopCfLvV6qoLWZvsd/edit#gid=89276578>

¹⁶ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1olzJCYFXvsrhAh45c0G91VkhOYt-TQ19/edit#gid=1088347470>

Table 3. RDA TIGER logos

	<p>The coloured version of the RDA TIGER logo with the EOSC co-branding should be used in all digital and printed project documentation and collaterals.</p> <p>The logo should be readable, in at least comparable size to other logos. It should not be distorted in any way.</p>
	<p>The monochrome version of the RDA TIGER logo (in black or white) may be used as an alternative stylistic choice when:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-branding requires it - Materials are printed in greyscale

An RDA TIGER illustration has been produced for marketing purposes and it can be found on the shared Google Drive²⁰.

Table 4. RDA TIGER ‘mascot’ illustration

	<p>The illustration can be used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standalone on unofficial digital and printed materials - Alongside the official EOSC co-branded logo in any official digital or printed materials. <p>Please note that the illustration is a marketing product and not a replacement for the official project logo.</p>
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²⁰ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1X0zduluMU5m509vYIR6872K-7l0dgUpY>

6.4. Communication Kit

The RDA TIGER communication kit is a combination of existing RDA communications materials available on the RDA website²¹ and new collaterals created for the promotion of the services specifically.

Table 5. RDA TIGER communication kit materials

Material	Description	Status
Branded slide deck	A slide deck to be used for all RDA TIGER related presentations by all partners.	Ongoing, will be part of D2.1 in month 6.
Acknowledgement for publications	The following attribution is to be used all all project outputs: "This work was developed as part of the RDA TIGER 'Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions', funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0 Grant Agreement 101094406, and we acknowledge the support provided within the project partners and resources".	Completed.
Branded roll-up banner	A roll-up banner to be used where RDA TIGER partners participate and/or present in events.	in progress, for completion by month 7.
Business cards	Business cards promoting RDA TIGER services.	Completed.
RDA TIGER illustration	An illustration to be used in unofficial marketing materials.	Completed, available on the shared Google Drive ²² .
RDA TIGER logo set	A logo set for RDA TIGER co-branded with the EOSC Association.	Completed, available on the shared Google Drive ²³ .
Zenodo community	The RDA TIGER project is going to use the 'RDA Related	Completed.

²¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/about-rda/communication-kit>

²² <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1X0zduluMU5m509vYIR6872K-7I0dgUpY>

²³ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1-RQKkRc_N5JV67InOnb9Wq9yW1AfwyWQ

Material	Description	Status
	Documents ²⁴ Zenodo community.	
Collection of newsletters	A collection of all newsletters issued throughout the project lifetime.	In progress.
Collection of presentations	A collection of all presentations delivered at events by project partners.	In progress.
Website	Project website to store and disseminate project results and plans.	Completed

6.5. Engagement and Outreach Tools

A number of general tools have been identified that can be utilised both for service awareness at a project level, and when working with each WG to deliver their communications strategies. This section will outline these tools.

Table 6. RDA TIGER communication kit materials

Tool	RDA TIGER service platform	RDA TIGER Communication Service
Webinars	Webinars will be organised to promote the RDA TIGER service, including the launch of Open Calls, ‘success stories’ (i.e., interviews and panel discussions with co-chairs discussing the services), etc.	Following assessment of each WG needs and requirements and in coordination with co-chairs, webinars may be implemented to promote specific Outputs.
Podcasts	<i>n/a</i>	Following assessment of each WG needs and requirements as well after analysing their audiences, and in coordination with co-chairs, podcasts will be considered for the promotion of specific Outputs.

²⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/rda-related/?page=1&size=20>

<p>In person conferences</p>	<p>RDA TIGER launched officially in January 2023, with the first marketing campaign taking place at RDA P20 in Gothenburg, where the RDA TIGER team utilising printed collaterals approached potential service users and worked on promoting the project. The project team has since leveraged other opportunities to drive service awareness (e.g., EGU23). RDA TIGER will also be present at the EOSC Symposium and the Open Science Fair in September 2023, as well as the International Data Week 2023, which will take place in Salzburg in October 202. In person opportunities will be continuously assessed and leveraged throughout the project.</p>	<p>RDA Plenaries will be utilised for specific Output promotion, but supported RDA WGs will be able to submit applications for travel grant and further funding; should WGs organise in person meetings via the RDA TIGER funding mechanisms, WP2 will endeavour to support the promotion efforts.</p>
<p>Social media</p>	<p>The RDA AISBL already has an online presence on Twitter and LinkedIn, and both of these avenues will be utilised in addition to the RDA Foundation’s channels. Partner social media (DANS, CODATA, eScienceCentre) will also be used for amplification purposes.</p>	<p>In addition to the social media channels available from the main Project partners, each supported WG will have their own accounts as well as those of their partner organisations.</p>
<p>Newsletters and bulletins</p>	<p>The RDA Global monthly newsletter²⁵ will be used as well as the ‘announcement’ functionality of the website²⁶. Project partners will also utilise their own newsletters and</p>	<p>A monthly ‘digest’ will be launched promoting RDA TIGER supported WG progress.</p>

²⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-newsletters>

²⁶ please note that due to the development of the new RDA website this process may change, but announcements to the RDA community will still be issued via whatever means available in the new solution.

	those of their partner organisations.	
Other projects and initiatives	<p>The EOSC Association²⁷ is working on creating connectivity between the EOSC-related projects. The EOSC Forum will be used to promote RDA TIGER results, Open Calls, press releases and any other relevant announcements.</p> <p>Other EC-funded projects will also be used for dissemination purposes, such as EOSC-FUTURE²⁸, FAIR-IMPACT²⁹ and WorldFAIR³⁰.</p>	Each WG has a different set of stakeholders, which will provide different routes for dissemination as well as additional needs. These will all be assessed with each supported WG. The results of the assessment will be recorded in the RDA TIGER Communications Coordination Spreadsheet ³¹ , and a report will be provided in due course.
Websites	The RDA ³² , CODATA ³³ , DANS ³⁴ and eScience Centre ³⁵ websites will be used for the publication of news RDA TIGER news, events, and general project updates as needed. In addition partner organisations' channels will also be leveraged, and in particular the very broad range of RDA Organisational and Affiliate members ³⁶	The project partner and related organisation websites will also be considered when creating bespoke communication strategies for each WG, and will be used as needed.

7. Exploitation of the project results

One potential route for exploitation of project outputs is the creation of Best Practice Guidelines for Facilitating an Expert Group.

²⁷ <https://eosc.eu>

²⁸ <https://eoscfuture.eu>

²⁹ <https://fair-impact.eu>

³⁰ <https://worldfair-project.eu/>

³¹ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1OKQcd3OrZWaqrI9OopCfLvV6qoLWZvsd/edit#gid=838946748>

³² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

³³ <https://codata.org/>

³⁴ <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/>

³⁵ <https://www.esciencecenter.nl/>

³⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/oa-members>

While not directly in scope within the RDA TIGER project, the success of the Facilitation support as a service offered to the RDA community is of strategic importance to the RDA AISBL and indeed the Global organisation; an assessment of the service effectiveness and reception will be carried out and examined from a sustainability perspective, with the long term goal of rolling out a similar service platform as a paid service and income stream for RDA EU/Global.

8. Monitoring and Performance

The following set of KPIs will be set for each WG supported by RDA TIGER. These KPIs are internal and will be treated as such.

Table 7. Communications KPIs for each supported WG

Key Performance Indicator	Observation Method	Target	WG stage
Social media sharing of WG ideas and call for membership - social media	Self-reporting	Weekly sharing of Group content across social media channels	(C1) WG starting
Sharing of WG ideas and call for membership - website posts	Self-reporting	Sharing of Group idea and call for membership on 3 partner websites (incl- RDA news items)	(C1) WG starting
Sharing of WG ideas and call for membership - events	Self-reporting	Presentation in at least 1 event (RDA or 3rd party)	(C1) WG starting
Sharing of WG ideas and call for membership - newsletters	Self-reporting	At least 1 item/month included in the RDA Global newsletter	(C1) WG starting
WG page unique views	Self-reporting	30 unique page views during C1 stage.	(C1) WG starting
New WG members	Self-reporting	20 (new) WG members by the end of the project.	(C1) WG starting
Unique group page views	Self-reporting	30 per month	C2 (WG Work period)
Creation of Group	Self-reporting	at least 5	C2 (WG Work period)

Key Performance Indicator	Observation Method	Target	WG stage
collaterals		communication campaigns/packages during project lifetime	
Group mention in RDA Global newsletter	Self-reporting	1 per quarter	C2 (WG Work period)
Social media mentions	Self-reporting	Weekly sharing of Group content across social media channels	C2 (WG Work period)
Event presence	Self-reporting	Participation/promotion in at least 5 events per year (not inc. RDA Plenaries) in any capacity (poster, lightning talk, paper, etc).	C2 (WG Work period)
Group-Internal newsletter and/or bulletin	Self-reporting	1 per month	C3 (WG end period)
Unique group page views	Self-reporting	50 for the duration of the project	C3 (WG end period)
Creation of Group collaterals	Self-reporting	at least 2 communication campaigns/packages during project lifetime	C3 (WG end period)
Group mention in RDA Global newsletter	Self-reporting	1 per Output stage	C3 (WG end period)
Social media mentions	Self-reporting	Weekly sharing of Group content across social media channels	C3 (WG end period)
Event presence	Self-reporting	Participation/promotion in at least 2 events per year (not inc. RDA Plenaries) in any capacity (poster, lightning talk, paper, etc).	C3 (WG end period)

Key Performance Indicator	Observation Method	Target	WG stage
Adoption outreach	Self-reporting	Target at least 2 adopters for each Recommendation via any means	C3 (WG end period)

The following KPIs will be measured as a minimum for the communications activities promoting the RDA TIGER service platform as a whole as well as project results.

Table 8. Communications KPIs for the RDA TIGER service platform

Key Performance Indicator	Observation Method	Target
Presentation of RDA TIGER in third party events during the project lifetime	Self-reporting	5
Webinars / drop-in sessions held around RDA TIGER Open Calls	Self-reporting	Minimum 3/year
Best practice guide	Self-reporting	1 report at month 12, and 1 update at month 36

Service reviews and user feedback

As part of WP6 Task 6.1 the service platform including the Communication service will undergo quality reviews. More details on the process will become available in D6.2 and D6.4.

9. Risks

WP2 has identified the following risks to the Strategy as presented in this document:

Table 9. RDA TIGER Risks and Mitigation Strategies

Risk Number	Description	Proposed mitigation measure
1	There is very high demand for communication services, and the project staffing status is not able to deliver.	Careful resourcing and service assessment during the Pilot stage enabling the RDA TIGER service platform to define the available capacity and manage expectations.

10. Conclusion

The RDA TIGER D2.2 ‘Updated Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities’ presented the high level strategic phases, priorities and impact for the RDA TIGER Communications, as well as the corresponding activities that WP2 work will focus on. The aim is to promote service awareness throughout the project, and provide quality communication services to RDA WGs. This WP will work closely and fluidly with the other services such as Facilitation and Landscaping; developing and delivering the service will be an iterative process drawing in experience from the pilot WGs as they develop.

